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ENHANCING HIGH-FLOW HYDROGEN REFUELING: MITIGATION OF PRESSURE LOSSES IN STORAGE AND DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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Abstract

High-flow hydrogen refuelling is essential for heavy-duty fuel cell electric vehicles but is hindered by significant pressure losses in storage and delivery systems. This study uses 1D simulations in GT-Suite with GEM-3D to analyse a hydrogen refuelling station modelled on an existing site in the Czech Republic. Initial designs showed high pressure drops, particularly in narrow or complex pipe sections. A redesigned bundle with larger diameters and simplified geometry reduced total pressure losses by over 50%, achieving sub-1 bar losses at 100–200 g/s. These findings support the development of efficient, high-flow hydrogen infrastructure in line with SAE J2601/5 standards.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) are essential for supporting fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs), delivering compressed hydrogen (typically 350 bar or 700 bar) into vehicle tanks. These stations must ensure not only rapid refuelling but also operational safety and efficiency comparable to conventional fuel stations. Core HRS technologies include hydrogen storage, either in high-pressure vessels (such as tube trailers) or as cryogenic liquid hydrogen vaporized and heated prior to dispensing [1],[2]. Achieving target fill pressures, particularly 700 bar for light-duty vehicles,

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necessitates the use of compressors, which are major energy consumers within the station [3],[4]. Rapid filling generates significant heat due to gas compression and the Joule-Thomson effect, requiring precooling of hydrogen to around $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to maintain vehicle tank temperatures below the safety threshold (typically $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for composite tanks) [5]. Dispensing is conducted through a nozzle-equipped dispenser with a control system that manages fill parameters (pressure, temperature, and flow) in compliance with standards such as SAE J2601.

One of the most critical challenges for HRS is the reliable and safe implementation of high-flow refuelling ($>65\text{ g/s}$), essential for heavy-duty applications like trucks and buses, where filling times must be minimized [6]. A major challenge for enabling high mass flow rates (above 65 g/s and up to 300 g/s) is managing pressure losses throughout the storage and dispensing systems. While standard flows for light-duty vehicles remain under 60 g/s , flows up to 300 g/s are increasingly targeted [7]. These high flow rates significantly intensify thermal loads, necessitating highly efficient cooling systems and advanced heat exchangers to maintain safe temperatures [1]. Pressure and flow management requires precise control of pressure ramps (as outlined in SAE J2601/5 for $60\text{--}300\text{ g/s}$) to mitigate pressure drops and flow instabilities. Elevated mass flows exacerbate pressure drops in pipelines and components, affecting the ability to maintain pressure ramp rates as specified by standards like SAE J2601/5 [7]. A lack of commercially available, standardized components (hoses, valves, nozzles) capable of handling flows above 65 g/s at 70 MPa remains a major barrier, underscoring the importance of interoperability between station and vehicle systems [6],[8]. Furthermore, these high flows substantially increase station energy demands—particularly for compressors and precooling—which impacts operational costs and the overall well-to-wheel carbon footprint [3],[4]. Materials challenges also intensify, as components must resist hydrogen embrittlement and other degradation mechanisms under high-pressure, low-temperature conditions [6]. Safety becomes increasingly critical, with higher hydrogen transfer volumes necessitating robust leak detection and rapid response capabilities. These technical and economic challenges result in significantly higher infrastructure costs for high-flow HRS [3].

Addressing these challenges is a focus of ongoing research and development. Standardization efforts, particularly by SAE International (e.g., SAE J2601/5, 2024), are instrumental in defining safe and efficient protocols for high-flow hydrogen fuelling. Advances in compression, cooling, and dispensing technologies will be essential to enabling rapid, safe, and economically viable hydrogen fuelling, especially for heavy-duty transport applications [1],[2].

2. 1D SIMULATION OF THE HYDROGEN REFUELING STATION

1D simulations are a very fast and efficient method for calculating pressure losses and parameters of the flow of complex systems such as hydrogen filling stations.

2.1 Description of the model

The simulation model is a hydrogen refuelling station with rapid fuelling based on the parameters of existing station situated in Vítkovice in Czech Republic. The modelled minimal required mass flow in this model is $60\text{ g H}_2/\text{s}$. Presented results were

obtained by simulations in GT-Suite software with usage the plug-in GEM-3D. The model of the station is shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Hydrogen refuelling station model

The simulations were carried out for different conditions such as initial and ambient conditions and initial pressure in the filled tank. The analysed part was the manifold connecting all bottles into one outgoing pipe.

Simulations were performed for various conditions, such as initial and ambient conditions and initial pressure in the filled tank. The main part analysed was the manifold connecting all cylinders to a single outlet pipe. Simulations were performed in the range of hydrogen outlet mass flow rates between 60 and 300 g/s and initial pressure in the cylinders between 150 and 300 bar. The initial pressure in the filled tank was set at 5 bar. The aim was to analyse the entire pipe and identify the most critical points in terms of pressure losses.

The creation of a model for pressure loss analysis required the conversion of the 3D geometry of the pipeline into a 1D simulation domain using the GEM-3D tool. From this, I then created a simulation model that can be used in the GT-Suite software environment. The converted geometry is shown in the following *Figure 2*.

Figure 2: Creating a bottle bundle model

The first design model of the bundle consisted of tubes with a diameter of 6 mm, which were then connected to a wider tube with a diameter of 12 mm (see *Figure 3*). This tube ran through the centre of the bundle and was shaped so that the outlet fitting of the bundle was in the desired position (both horizontal and vertical).

Figure 3: Hydrogen bottle bundle model

2.2 Results

The first simulations showed that the initial configuration of the cylinder bundle resulted in excessively high pressure losses, and such a bundle would not be suitable for the planned filling station. The greatest pressure losses were achieved on the central tube before the outlet from the bundle. This pressure loss amounted to 5.68 bar for 300 bar in cylinders and a mass flow of 60 g/s. The second most critical point was the connection of the first pair of cylinders in the bundle. This pressure loss was 5.17 bar. The most critical points are shown in the following *Figure 4*.

Figure 4: The most critical points of the original bottle bundle design

It was therefore necessary to design a new bundle configuration to increase the flow cross-sections and reduce the overall pressure loss of the bundle. It was proposed to increase the pipe diameter to 14 mm and remove as many pipe bends as possible, which also have a negative impact on pressure losses. The modified bundle design is shown in the *Figure 5*.

Figure 5: The modified bottle bundle

The modified design showed significant improvement in terms of pressure losses across the entire spectrum of cases monitored. The highest total pressure loss for the entire cylinder bundle is 4.3 bar for 150 bar in cylinders and a mass flow rate of 300 g/s. However, in reality, the bundle never reaches these extreme values, which are only limit values. Based on these simulations, it can be said that a total pressure loss of less than 1 bar can be achieved when discharging 100 g/s and 200 g/s in all conditions; when discharging at a higher mass flow rate, these losses are higher. The results are shown in *Figure 6*.

Figure 6: Total pressure loss of the bottle bundle

The highest partial pressure losses were again achieved on parts of the central pipe. Subsequently, the pipe before connecting to a single pipe and its adjacent elbow. These locations are again shown in the figure below (see *Figure 7*) and the course of these losses in the *Figure 8*.

Figure 7: Location of the most critical points of the bundle

Figure 8: The most critical points of the bundle

3. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates that effective mitigation of pressure losses is essential for enabling high-flow hydrogen refuelling, particularly for applications exceeding 100 g/s such as buses and trucks. Through detailed 1D simulations of hydrogen refuelling station pipelines, it was shown that pressure losses are most pronounced in the narrow and geometrically complex sections of the gas delivery system—especially at central manifolds and pipe junctions.

The original cylinder bundle design exhibited excessive pressure losses that would critically impair the station’s ability to deliver hydrogen at high flow rates. The redesign, featuring increased pipe diameters (14 mm) and reduced curvature, led to a substantial improvement in performance. Pressure losses were reduced to below 1 bar under standard operating conditions (100–200 g/s), thus ensuring compliance with current high-flow fuelling protocols such as SAE J2601/5.

This study underscores the necessity of precise hydraulic modelling and careful geometric optimization in the design of future hydrogen refuelling infrastructure. Continued research in advanced simulation and component standardization will be key to overcoming technical barriers and supporting the widespread deployment of hydrogen-powered heavy-duty transportation.

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